

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Effect of ultrasonication on waste activated sludge rheological properties and process economics

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Table S1. Main characteristics of the thickened WAS sample. Errors represent standard deviation (n=3)

Parameter	Value
TS (g/kg)	56.2±0.4
VS (g/kg)	46.6±0.6
Total COD (g O ₂ /L)	80.9±0.4
Soluble COD (g O ₂ /L)	0.9±0.1
pH	6.5±0.2
Soluble protein (mg/L)	416
CST (s)	1,562

Table S2. Economic parameters used for cost calculation

	Value	Reference
Capital cost ultrasound reactor (€/kW)	7,500	Lippert et al., 2021
Energy consumption ultrasound reactor (kJ/kg TS)	200	Lippert et al., 2021
Lifetime ultrasound reactor (years)	3	Lippert et al., 2021
Electrical efficiency CHP unit (%)	33	Riley et al., 2020
Methane calorific value (MJ/kg)	55.5	Batstone et al., 2015
Electricity cost (€/kWh)	0.1149	Eurostat, 2019
Capital cost CHP unit upgrading (€/kW _{el})	712	Riley et al., 2020
Operating cost CHP unit (€/kWh _{el})	0.0119	Riley et al., 2020
Polyelectrolyte dosage (kg/t TS)	9	Vinardell et al., 2021
Polyelectrolyte cost (€/kg)	2.35	Pretel et al., 2014
Centrifuge energy consumption (kWh/kg TSS)	0.045	Pretel et al., 2014
Biosolids disposal cost (including transport) (€/t TS)	147	Vinardell et al., 2021
Energy consumption mainstream nitrogen removal (kWh/kg N)	2.38	Horstmeyer et al., 2018
Ferric chloride cost (€/t)	220	Taboada-Santos et al., 2020

Baseline Scenario

Scenario 1

Figure S1. Schematic representation of the two scenarios evaluated in the economic analysis: (top) Baseline Scenario, which did not implement ultrasonication for WAS pre-treatment, and (bottom) Scenario 1, which implemented ultrasonication for WAS pre-treatment.

References

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